

Progress Report: Towards European LLMs

Mehdi Ali^{1,2†} Michael Fromm^{1,2†} Klaudia Thellmann^{3†} Jan Ebert^{4†} Alexander Arno Weber^{1,2†}
Richard Rutmann^{1,2} Charvi Jain^{1,2} Max Lübbering^{1,2} Daniel Steinigen¹ Johannes Leveling¹ Katrin Klug¹
Jasper Schulze Buschhoff¹ Lena Jurkschat³ Hammam Abdelwahab¹ Benny Jörg Stein¹
Karl-Heinz¹ Sylla Pavel Denisov¹ Nicolo Brandizzi¹ Qasid Saleem¹ Bhowmick Anirban¹
Chelsea John⁴ Pedro Ortiz Suarez⁵ Malte Ostendorff⁵ Alex Jude¹ Lalith Manjunath³
Samuel Weinbach⁷ Carolin Penke⁴ Shima Asaadi⁶ Fabio Barth⁵ Rafet Sifa¹ Fabian Küch⁶
René Jäkel⁵ Georg Rehm⁵ Stefan Kesselheim⁴ Joachim Köhler¹ Nicolas Flores-Herr¹
¹Fraunhofer IAIS ²Lamarr Institute ³TU Dresden ⁴FZ Jülich ⁵DFKI ⁶Fraunhofer IIS ⁷Aleph Alpha

Abstract

We present preliminary results of the project OpenGPT-X. At present, the project has developed two multilingual Large Language Models (LLMs) designed to embrace Europe’s linguistic diversity by supporting all 24 official languages of the European Union. Trained on a dataset comprising around 60% non-English data and utilizing a custom multilingual tokenizer, our models address the limitations of existing LLMs that predominantly focus on English or a few high-resource languages. We detail the models’ development principles, data processing techniques, tokenizer optimization, and training methodologies. The models demonstrate competitive performance across multilingual benchmarks, as evidenced by its performance on European versions of ARC, HellaSwag, MMLU, and TruthfulQA.

1 Introduction

LLMs represents a disruptive technology that has the potential to be applied in numerous applications. Therefore, it is crucial that the technology and expertise to build these models is democratized to enable different communities and organizations to employ these models for their use cases. Many efforts in developing open-source LLMs have been undertaken, such as BLOOM (Scao et al., 2022), LLaMA-3 (Dubey et al., 2024), OLMo (Groeneveld et al., 2024), Aya (Üstün et al., 2024), and Mistral (Jiang et al., 2023). These can be split into efforts focusing on building monolingual English models and efforts focusing on multilingual models.

The current open-source models are predominantly English-centric, limiting their use in a multilingual context such as within the European Union. Furthermore, the open-source efforts disclose different levels of granularity regarding sharing details about the development of the models. While

information regarding the model architecture is usually shared, the dataset composition and filtering are often not described in detail, hindering the reproduction of the works.

To address the aforementioned limitations, we present our effort in developing a multilingual base model that has been trained on top of all 24 European official languages and the corresponding instruction-tuned model. The results represent our preliminary results. An open-source publication of the models is planned for the near future.

2 Related Work

Since the introduction of GPT-3 (Brown et al., 2020), several open-source/open-weights efforts have been undertaken to train LLMs. While the large majority of the work focus on English-centric models (Zhang et al., 2022; Touvron et al., 2023a,b; Groeneveld et al., 2024; Dubey et al., 2024), there have been also efforts training multilingual models.

One of the most prominent examples is BLOOM (Scao et al., 2022), a 176B LLM trained on 46 natural languages. Further examples that specifically address multilingualism are the encoder-decoder models mT5 (Xue et al., 2021), XLM (Lample and Conneau, 2019), XLM-R (Conneau et al., 2020), and the encoder model mBERT (Devlin et al., 2019).

Unlike the previously mentioned efforts, we specifically address 24 official European languages and focus on ensuring that a large fraction of the training data is composed of non-English data, representing a major step towards European LLMs. Concurrent to our work, EuroLLM (Martins et al., 2024), a 1.7B decoder-only LLM that follows the same spirit as our undertaking by addressing all 24 European languages, has been presented.

[†]Equal contribution.

3 Pre-Training Data

Our training dataset contains approximately 4 trillion tokens, of which 13.45% is curated data (cf. Table 9), while the remaining 86.55% (cf. Table 8) originates from web data. We generated our web data by processing 60 WET dumps (cf. Appendix A.1.1) from CommonCrawl with the Ungoliant pipeline (Abadji et al., 2022). The resulting web documents were additionally filtered by removing all documents with *at least one* quality warning¹ and harmful perplexities *smaller than 5*. We removed around 90% of the documents by filtering based on these annotations. In a final step, we performed MinHash deduplication and further removed 50% of the filtered documents.

Regarding language distribution, the dataset covers all 24 official European languages. As illustrated in Figure 1 and Figure 2, 41.70% of the tokens stem from English content. By additionally including German, French, and Spanish, we approach around two-thirds of the total tokens.

We found that there is a strong correlation between the volume of linguistic data and the population of the countries where these languages are spoken, with a correlation coefficient of 0.987 ($P < .001$)².

4 Multilingual Tokenization and Fertility Impact on Model Efficiency

In multilingual natural language processing (NLP), it is crucial to train balanced multilingual tokenizers (Petrov et al., 2023; Ali et al., 2024). English-centric tokenizers or unbalanced multilingual tokenizers affect inference costs and latency during inference for non-English queries. Furthermore, it prevents the model from learning long-range dependencies in limited context windows (Vaswani et al., 2017).

To address these limitations, we developed a custom multilingual tokenizer, closely following Ali et al. (2024), that is optimized for all 24 official European languages. It aims to reduce excessive text fragmentation. This phenomenon, termed as high "fertility", refers to the average number of tokens generated per word.

Fertility (F) is defined as the ratio of the total number of tokens (T) to the total number of words

¹The Ungoliant pipeline annotates documents with the following warnings: tiny, noisy, header, footer, and short_sentences, see Abadji et al. (2022)

²Population data sourced from EU stats, accessed in September 2024.

(W) in a text, as shown in the following equation:

$$F = \frac{T}{W}$$

We conducted a fertility analysis on 2,000 sentences from the FLORES-200 dataset to compare tokenizers. Because the dataset is translated across languages, i.e., the analysis is conducted on semantic equivalent content, it provides a reliable basis for evaluation. A comparison with other widely-used tokenizers is presented in Figure 3

Our custom tokenizer demonstrates that for 19 out of the 24 languages, fertility values are similar to or lower than those of related tokenizers. This effect is especially pronounced in languages with complex morphology or long word structures, such as Finnish, German, and Hungarian.

Lowering fertility enables longer queries and documents to be processed without exceeding the context window. This is particularly advantageous in tasks that require the processing of legal or medical documents, where maintaining the integrity of long documents is essential for accurate understanding.

5 Base Model

In the following, we describe the model architecture and training (Section 5.1), the used training framework (Section 5.2), and the training infrastructure (Section 5.3).

5.1 Model Architecture & Training

Our model is a 7B transformer-based decoder-only model. Table 1 provides an overview of our model architecture. We want to highlight some of the architectural choices that are derived from internal ablation studies and findings from related work. Our models have a sequence length of 4096 tokens and employ Rotary (Su et al., 2024) positional embeddings that are employed to train state-of-the-art models (Dubey et al., 2024). To accelerate inference and reduce memory requirements, we employed grouped query attention (Ainslie et al., 2023).

Using the causal language modelling training objective, we trained our model on 4T tokens covering all 24 European languages as described in Section 3. As an optimizer, we employed AdamW and used a cosine learning rate schedule starting with learning rate of 3e-5, increasing it to the maximum learning rate of 3e-4 within the first 10,000 steps, and decaying it afterwards.

Figure 1: Language distribution of the tokenized dataset, comparing the presence of English and other European languages.

Figure 2: Breakdown of the "OTHER" category.

5.2 Software

We selected our training framework based on efficiency in terms of throughput (TFLOP/s) and maintenance. Therefore, we decided to train our models based on a fork of MegatronLM (Korthikanti et al., 2023) that supports various scalability features ensuring efficient training of transformer-based decoder-only models. In particular, we made use of 3D parallelism, i.e., data, tensor, and pipeline parallelism. Additionally, we used ZeRO (Korthikanti et al., 2023) to reduce memory requirements further by sharding the optimizer state.

5.3 Training Infrastructure

We trained our models on JUWELS Booster³ that comprises 936 compute nodes, each of which contains $4 \times$ NVIDIA A100 (40 GB) GPUs connected via NVLink3 intra-node, and through Mellanox HDR200 InfiniBand inter-node. For our training runs, we utilized up to 512 GPUs.

6 Instruction Tuned Model

In this section, we describe the creation of the instruction tuned model, including the dataset com-

position (cf. section 6.1), the instruction tuning (cf. section 6.2) and the evaluation (cf. section 6.3).

6.1 Data

The dataset for instruction tuning is composed of English data translated into German, English data, and multilingual data covering all 24 official European languages. The dataset is composed of several subsets, as listed in Table 2.

English To select high-quality English data, we employed a rigorous multi-step filtering process. First, we computed reward scores for all English examples using Starling-RM-7B-alpha⁴. Our objective was to balance the dataset, aiming to include a similar number of English and multilingual examples. We achieved this by including all multi-turn examples, the complete code alpaca⁵ subset, and the entire high-quality portion of the LMSYS-Chat dataset subset. For the remaining subsets — Open Orca and both versions of the Evol instruct datasets — we selected the highest-scoring examples to ensure that each subset contributed an equal amount of high-quality data.

³<https://jlsrf.org/index.php/lsf/article/view/171>

⁴<https://huggingface.co/berkeley-nest/Starling-RM-7B-alpha>

Figure 3: Fertility across the official 24 European languages.

Multilingual For the multilingual data selection, we incorporated several datasets to ensure broad linguistic coverage. We included data from the 17 official EU languages present in the Bactrian-X dataset, as Weber et al. (2024) demonstrated that semantically parallel data enhances cross-lingual model performance. Additionally, we integrated the 14 official EU languages from the Aya Dataset and the 21 official EU languages from the translated FLAN-CoT subset of the Aya Collection. With this selection, we cover all 24 EU languages.

Translation to German Since large-scale German instruction-tuning data is less abundant, the English portion of the dataset was translated into German using the Alma-13B (Xu et al., 2024) model. To preserve the integrity of code snippets during the translation process, a regex-based code detection method was implemented. This ensured that code was excluded from translation and then reinserted afterward, allowing for a faithful German version of the dataset.

Hyper-Parameter	Value
Training Objective	CLM
Activation Function	SwiGLU
Seq Length	4096
Position Embeddings	Rotary
Num Layers	32
Hidden Size	4096
FFN Hidden Size	13440
Num Attention Heads	32
Head Dim	128
Group Query Attention	yes
Num Query Groups	2
Normalization	RMSNorm
Learning rate	3e-4
Min learning rate	3e-5
Disable bias in linear	yes
Hidden dropout	0.0
Attention dropout	0.0
Optimizer	AdamW
Beta1	0.9
Beta2	0.95
Data-type	bf16
Recompute-activations	yes
Distributed-optimizers	yes

Table 1: Hyper-Parameter Configuration

6.2 Post-Training

For instruction-tuning the model, we extended FastChat⁵ for multilingual system prompts and translated the system prompt "A chat between a human and an artificial intelligence assistant. The assistant gives helpful and polite answers to the human's questions." for all 24 official EU languages. We employed standard instruction tuning by calculating the loss only for the assistant responses of a multi-turn conversation. We trained the model on 8xH100 GPUs for 2.5 days for three epochs.

6.3 Multilingual Instruction Evaluation

For evaluating the multilingual instruction-following capabilities of the model, we utilized MT-Bench-X (Weber et al., 2024) across all five available evaluation languages: English, German, French, Italian, and Spanish. The results are presented in the Appendix A.2. While the creative writing skills of the model show good performance, the mathematical, coding, and reasoning skills are inferior across languages.

⁵<https://github.com/lm-sys/FastChat/tree/main/fastchat>

Subset	Language	Count	Ø Turns
CohereForAI/aya_collection	Multilingual	39.9K	1.0
MBZUAI/Bactrian-X	Multilingual	32.3K	1.0
CohereForAI/aya_dataset	Multilingual	13.1K	1.0
anon8231489123/ShareGPT_Vicuna_unfiltered	EN	37.7K	4.6
sahil2801/CodeAlpaca-20k	EN	12.1K	1.0
lmsys/lmsys-chat-1m	EN	11.2K	1.5
WizardLM/WizardLM_evolution_instruct_V2_196k	EN	8.1K	1.0
Open-Orca/OpenOrca	EN	8.1K	1.0
WizardLM/WizardLM_evolution_instruct_70k	EN	8.1K	1.0
HuggingFaceH4/ultrachat_200k	EN	6.9K	3.1
anon8231489123/ShareGPT_Vicuna_unfiltered	transl. DE	37.6K	4.6
lmsys/lmsys-chat-1m	transl. DE	11.2K	1.5
WizardLM/WizardLM_evolution_instruct_70k	transl. DE	8.1K	1.0
Open-Orca/OpenOrca	transl. DE	8.1K	1.0
WizardLM/WizardLM_evolution_instruct_V2_196k	transl. DE	8.1K	1.0
HuggingFaceH4/ultrachat_200k	transl. DE	6.9K	3.1
FreedomIntelligence/sharegpt-deutsch	DE	5.7K	2.9
bjoernp/ultrachat_de	DE	905	1.0

Table 2: Instruction-tuning training dataset composition.

7 Results

In this section, we describe the results of our base and instruction-tuned models. We focus on a multilingual evaluation because our effort targets multilingualism, especially in the official European languages.

We conducted our evaluation based on ARC (Clark et al., 2018), HellaSwag (Zellers et al., 2019), TruthfulQA (Lin et al., 2022), and MMLU (Hendrycks et al., 2021) which has been translated into 21 out of 24 official European languages providing a comprehensive assessment of the models’ capabilities. We compared our models on these benchmarks against Aya-23-8B, LLaMA 3.1 8B, LLaMA 3.1 8B Instruct, Mistral 7B v0.3, and Mistral 7B Instruct v0.3. Note that the Mistral models compared to in this study were not trained as multilingual models and are intended to be used as English-only models. Results from other models are available on the European Leaderboard⁶.

Section 7.1 presents our results across all investigated 21 languages, Section 7.2 discusses the performance of our models on the six widely spoken languages English, German, French, Italian, Spanish, and Portuguese, and Section 7.3 presents

our results on the remaining 15 languages.

7.1 Performance on 21 European Languages

In Table 3, we present the performance of various language models on multilingual benchmarks across 21 European languages.

Ours (Instruct) demonstrates strong performance, particularly excelling in the ARC and HellaSwag benchmarks. It achieves the highest accuracy on HellaSwag with 62.1%, outperforming all other models. On the ARC benchmark, "Ours (Instruct)" also attains the top score of 57.6%, indicating superior reasoning and commonsense understanding in multilingual contexts. This suggests that our instruction-tuning approach effectively enhances the model’s ability to handle diverse languages in complex reasoning tasks.

However, Ours (Instruct) shows a lower performance on the MMLU benchmark, scoring 44.1%, which is below the scores of LLaMA 3.1 8B Instruct (57.6%) and LLaMA 3.1 8B (55.6%). This indicates that while our model excels in certain areas, there is room for improvement in domain-specific knowledge across multiple languages. On TruthfulQA, "Ours (Instruct)" achieves a moderate score of 51.1%, which is competitive but still trails behind Mistral 7B Instruct v0.3 (54.8%) and

⁶<https://huggingface.co/spaces/openGPT-X/european-llm-leaderboard>

Model	Average	ARC	HellaSwag	TruthfulQA	MMLU
Aya-23-8B	.485	.475 ± .134	.535 ± .145	.476 ± .028	.455 ± .070
LLaMA 3.1 8B	.547	.554 ± .071	.588 ± .090	.495 ± .026	.556 ± .047
LLaMA 3.1 8B Instruct	.563	.563 ± .075	.579 ± .089	.532 ± .023	.576 ± .051
Mistral 7B v0.3	.505	.513 ± .128	.534 ± .124	.472 ± .034	.501 ± .075
Mistral 7B Instruct v0.3	.527	.530 ± .136	.538 ± .129	.548 ± .048	.490 ± .075
Ours (Base)	.496	.550 ± .043	.615 ± .048	.469 ± .031	.349 ± .024
Ours (Instruct)	.537	.576 ± .047	.621 ± .052	.511 ± .019	.441 ± .022

Table 3: Results on multilingual benchmarks for 21 European languages, including mean accuracy and corresponding standard deviations across languages.

LLaMA 3.1 8B Instruct (53.2%).

The average score of "Ours (Instruct)" is 53.7%, placing it below LLaMA 3.1 8B Instruct (56.3%) but above Mistral 7B Instruct v0.3 (52.7%). The standard deviations across the languages are relatively low for our models, suggesting more consistent performance across different European languages compared to models like Aya-23-8B and Mistral 7B variants, which exhibit higher variability. This consistency is crucial for applications requiring reliable performance in multilingual settings.

In summary, "Ours (Instruct)" shows promising results, particularly in reasoning and commonsense tasks, and maintains consistent performance across languages. Further work is needed to enhance its domain-specific knowledge and truthfulness in responses to match or surpass the leading models in all benchmarks.

7.2 Performance on Common European Languages

Table 4 focuses on the performance of the models on six widely spoken European languages: English, German, French, Italian, Spanish, and Portuguese. These languages are well-represented in training data and are commonly used in evaluating multilingual models.

Ours (Instruct) model achieves an average score of 56.9%, which is lower than the top-performing LLaMA 3.1 8B Instruct model at 62.3%. However, it should be highlighted that our model has been trained based on around 4T tokens, which is significantly less data than LLaMA 3.1 8B, which has been trained on 15T tokens. The training dataset sizes of the other models are not revealed. Notably, "Ours (Instruct)" performs competitively on the HellaSwag benchmark, attaining 67.9%, which is slightly higher than LLaMA 3.1 8B Instruct

(67.7%) and Mistral 7B Instruct v0.3 (67.0%). This reinforces our model’s strength in understanding and generating coherent continuations in context-rich scenarios.

On the ARC benchmark, "Ours (Instruct)" scores 63.2%, which is close to Mistral 7B Instruct v0.3 (65.4%) and LLaMA 3.1 8B Instruct (64.8%), indicating good performance in multiple-choice question answering. However, in the MMLU benchmark, our model scores 46.5%, which is significantly lower than LLaMA 3.1 8B Instruct’s 63.2%. This suggests that our model may have limitations in specialized knowledge domains within these common languages.

For TruthfulQA, "Ours (Instruct)" achieves 49.9%, below Mistral 7B Instruct v0.3’s 56.8% and LLaMA 3.1 8B Instruct’s 53.5%. This indicates that while our model is proficient in generating plausible responses, it may sometimes sacrifice factual accuracy, highlighting an area for improvement in ensuring truthfulness.

Overall, "Ours (Instruct)" demonstrates strong capabilities in certain tasks within common European languages but falls short in others compared to the leading models. Enhancing its domain-specific knowledge and factual accuracy could help bridge this performance gap.

7.3 Performance on Exclusive European Languages

Table 5 presents the models’ performance on 15 less commonly evaluated European languages, which we refer to as exclusive languages. These include Romanian, Czech, Danish, Greek, Estonian, Finnish, Hungarian, Lithuanian, Latvian, Dutch, Bulgarian, Polish, Slovak, Slovenian, and Swedish.

In this setting, our "Ours (Instruct)" model is on average slightly behind LLaMA 3.1 8B Instruct mainly due to our performance on MMLU indi-

Model	Average	ARC	HellaSwag	TruthfulQA	MMLU
Aya-23-8B	.574	.614 ± .029	.687 ± .047	.470 ± .023	.526 ± .019
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.601	.634 ± .042	.687 ± .067	.474 ± .015	.607 ± .027
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.623	.648 ± .045	.677 ± .064	.535 ± .016	.632 ± .029
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.613	.654 ± .050	.670 ± .088	.568 ± .015	.560 ± .033
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.580	.632 ± .048	.662 ± .084	.453 ± .016	.571 ± .031
Ours (Base)	.521	.599 ± .038	.667 ± .042	.445 ± .017	.371 ± .023
Ours (Instruct)	.569	.632 ± .033	.679 ± .043	.499 ± .018	.465 ± .015

Table 4: Results on multilingual benchmarks for six Languages (English, German, French, Italian, Spanish, Portuguese) including mean accuracy and corresponding standard deviations across languages.

cating that learning domain-specific knowledge in exclusive languages is an area for improvement. At the same time, our model obtains the strongest results on the ARC (56.3%) and HellaSwag (60.8%) benchmarks among all evaluated models. This suggests that our model is particularly effective in reasoning and understanding context in less commonly represented languages, which is a significant achievement given the challenges associated with limited training data in these languages. On TruthfulQA, "Ours (Instruct)" attains 51.3%, which is competitive but still trails behind Mistral 7B Instruct v0.3's 54.3%.

The standard deviations for our models are lower compared to others, reflecting more consistent performance across the exclusive languages. This consistency is crucial for real-world applications where reliability across languages is necessary.

In conclusion, "Ours (Instruct)" exhibits excellent reasoning and contextual understanding in less commonly evaluated European languages, outperforming other models in specific benchmarks. Enhancing its knowledge base and factual accuracy in these languages could further elevate its overall performance.

7.4 Comparison with Aya-23-8B on Common Languages

Table 6 compares our models with Aya-23-8B on 11 common European languages shared between the datasets used by both models. These languages include Czech, Dutch, English, French, German, Greek, Italian, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, and Spanish.

Our "Ours (Instruct)" model achieves an average score of 55.5% competitive to Aya-23-8B's 56.3%. On the ARC benchmark, "Ours (Instruct)" surpasses Aya-23-8B with a score of 60.6% compared to 59.3%, demonstrating strong reasoning

abilities in these languages. Additionally, "Ours (Instruct)" attains a higher score on TruthfulQA (51.2% vs. 48.5%).

However, Aya-23-8B outperforms our model on the HellaSwag benchmark with a score of 66.0% versus "Ours (Instruct)" at 65.1%. Aya-23-8B also leads on the MMLU benchmark with 51.3%, compared to our model's 45.2%. These results suggest that while "Ours (Instruct)" is competitive, particularly in reasoning and truthfulness, there is room for improvement in contextual understanding and domain-specific knowledge.

Our "Ours (Base)" model, without instruction tuning, achieves an average score of 51.1%, which is lower than both "Ours (Instruct)" and Aya-23-8B. This highlights the effectiveness of instruction tuning in enhancing the model's performance across multiple tasks and languages.

In summary, "Ours (Instruct)" is competitive to Aya-23-8B in common European languages, especially in reasoning tasks and truthfulness. Continued refinement and training could further improve its performance, making it a more robust model for multilingual applications.

8 Conclusion

In this work, we presented the development of two multilingual large language models, "Ours (Base)" and "Ours (Instruct)", tailored to support the linguistic diversity of Europe by encompassing all 24 official EU languages. Through the use of a custom multilingual tokenizer and a dataset prioritizing non-English content, our models address limitations found in existing multilingual models, particularly their English-centric bias. Preliminary results demonstrate competitive performance across multiple benchmarks, including ARC, HellaSwag, MMLU, and TruthfulQA.

Our ongoing efforts aim to further improve the

Model	Average	ARC	HellaSwag	TruthfulQA	MMLU
Aya-23-8B	.460	.435 ± .130	.493 ± .142	.477 ± .030	.436 ± .070
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.536	.534 ± .070	.566 ± .092	.500 ± .028	.543 ± .047
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.548	.542 ± .075	.556 ± .090	.531 ± .025	.562 ± .051
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.505	.497 ± .141	.508 ± .134	.543 ± .055	.473 ± .078
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.486	.482 ± .132	.504 ± .128	.476 ± .038	.483 ± .078
Ours (Base)	.491	.540 ± .045	.603 ± .050	.474 ± .034	.345 ± .026
Ours (Instruct)	.530	.563 ± .046	.608 ± .054	.513 ± .021	.436 ± .022

Table 5: Results on multilingual benchmarks across the 15 exclusive European languages (Romanian, Czech, Danish, Greek, Estonian, Finnish, Hungarian, Lithuanian, Latvian, Dutch, Bulgarian, Polish, Slovak, Slovenian, and Swedish.). The results depict mean accuracy and corresponding standard deviations across languages.

Model	Average	ARC	HellaSwag	TruthfulQA	MMLU
Aya-23-8B	.563	.593 ± .032	.660 ± .047	.485 ± .028	.513 ± .022
Ours (Base)	.511	.578 ± .037	.642 ± .043	.464 ± .027	.361 ± .024
Ours (Instruct)	.555	.606 ± .038	.651 ± .045	.512 ± .021	.452 ± .021

Table 6: Results on multilingual benchmarks across the 11 common languages (Czech, Dutch, English, French, German, Greek, Italian, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, and Spanish.) with Aya-23. It includes mean accuracy and corresponding standard deviations across languages.

models’ performance and efficiency, ensuring they can better serve the needs of diverse European communities and facilitate the broader democratization of LLM technology across multilingual environments. Future work will focus on improving the models in specialized knowledge domains, math and code capabilities.

References

Julien Abadji, Pedro Ortiz Suarez, Laurent Romary, and Benoît Sagot. 2022. [Towards a cleaner document-oriented multilingual crawled corpus](#). In *Proceedings of the Thirteenth Language Resources and Evaluation Conference*, pages 4344–4355, Marseille, France. European Language Resources Association.

Joshua Ainslie, James Lee-Thorp, Michiel de Jong, Yury Zemlyanskiy, Federico Lebrón, and Sumit Sanghai. 2023. GQA: training generalized multi-query transformer models from multi-head checkpoints. In *EMNLP*, pages 4895–4901. Association for Computational Linguistics.

Mehdi Ali, Michael Fromm, Klaudia Thellmann, Richard Rutmann, Max Lübbering, Johannes Leveling, Katrin Klug, Jan Ebert, Niclas Doll, Jasper Buschhoff, Charvi Jain, Alexander Weber, Lena Jurkschat, Hammam Abdelwahab, Chelsea John, Pedro Ortiz Suarez, Malte Ostendorff, Samuel Weinbach, Rafet Sifa, Stefan Kesselheim, and Nicolas Flores-Herr. 2024. [Tokenizer choice for LLM training: Negligible or crucial?](#) In *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: NAACL 2024*, pages

3907–3924, Mexico City, Mexico. Association for Computational Linguistics.

Tom B. Brown, Benjamin Mann, Nick Ryder, Melanie Subbiah, Jared Kaplan, Prafulla Dhariwal, Arvind Neelakantan, Pranav Shyam, Girish Sastry, Amanda Askell, Sandhini Agarwal, Ariel Herbert-Voss, Gretchen Krueger, Tom Henighan, Rewon Child, Aditya Ramesh, Daniel M. Ziegler, Jeffrey Wu, Clemens Winter, Christopher Hesse, Mark Chen, Eric Sigler, Mateusz Litwin, Scott Gray, Benjamin Chess, Jack Clark, Christopher Berner, Sam McCandlish, Alec Radford, Ilya Sutskever, and Dario Amodei. 2020. Language models are few-shot learners. In *NeurIPS*.

Peter Clark, Isaac Cowhey, Oren Etzioni, Tushar Khot, Ashish Sabharwal, Carissa Schoenick, and Oyvind Tafjord. 2018. Think you have solved question answering? try arc, the AI2 reasoning challenge. *CoRR*, abs/1803.05457.

Alexis Conneau, Kartikay Khandelwal, Naman Goyal, Vishrav Chaudhary, Guillaume Wenzek, Francisco Guzmán, Edouard Grave, Myle Ott, Luke Zettlemoyer, and Veselin Stoyanov. 2020. [Unsupervised cross-lingual representation learning at scale](#). In *Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, pages 8440–8451, Online. Association for Computational Linguistics.

Jacob Devlin, Ming-Wei Chang, Kenton Lee, and Kristina Toutanova. 2019. [BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding](#). In *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for*

Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long and Short Papers), pages 4171–4186, Minneapolis, Minnesota. Association for Computational Linguistics.

Abhimanyu Dubey, Abhinav Jauhri, Abhinav Pandey, Abhishek Kadian, Ahmad Al-Dahle, Aiesha Letman, Akhil Mathur, Alan Schelten, Amy Yang, Angela Fan, Anirudh Goyal, Anthony Hartshorn, Aobo Yang, Archi Mitra, Archie Sravankumar, Artem Korenev, Arthur Hinsvark, Arun Rao, Aston Zhang, Aurelien Rodriguez, Austen Gregerson, Ava Spataru, Baptiste Roziere, Bethany Biron, Binh Tang, Bobbie Chern, Charlotte Caucheteux, Chaya Nayak, Chloe Bi, Chris Marra, Chris McConnell, Christian Keller, Christophe Touret, Chunyang Wu, Corinne Wong, Cristian Canton Ferrer, Cyrus Nikolaidis, Damien Allonsius, Daniel Song, Danielle Pintz, Danny Livshits, David Esiobu, Dhruv Choudhary, Dhruv Mahajan, Diego Garcia-Olano, Diego Perino, Dieuwke Hupkes, Egor Lakomkin, Ehab AlBadawy, Elina Lobanova, Emily Dinan, Eric Michael Smith, Filip Radenovic, Frank Zhang, Gabriel Synnaeve, Gabrielle Lee, Georgia Lewis Anderson, Graeme Nail, Gregoire Mialon, Guan Pang, Guillem Cucurell, Hailey Nguyen, Hannah Korevaar, Hu Xu, Hugo Touvron, Iliyan Zarov, Imanol Arrieta Ibarra, Isabel Kloumann, Ishan Misra, Ivan Evtimov, Jade Copet, Jaewon Lee, Jan Geffert, Jana Vranes, Jason Park, Jay Mahadeokar, Jeet Shah, Jelmer van der Linde, Jennifer Billock, Jenny Hong, Jenya Lee, Jeremy Fu, Jennifeng Chi, Jianyu Huang, Jiawen Liu, Jie Wang, Jiecao Yu, Joanna Bitton, Joe Spisak, Jongsoo Park, Joseph Rocca, Joshua Johnstun, Joshua Saxe, Jung-teng Jia, Kalyan Vasuden Alwala, Kartikeya Upasani, Kate Plawiak, Ke Li, Kenneth Heafield, Kevin Stone, Khalid El-Arini, Krithika Iyer, Kshitiz Malik, Kuenley Chiu, Kunal Bhalla, Lauren Rantala-Yearly, Laurens van der Maaten, Lawrence Chen, Liang Tan, Liz Jenkins, Louis Martin, Lovish Madaan, Lubo Malo, Lukas Blecher, Lukas Landzaat, Luke de Oliveira, Madeline Muzzi, Mahesh Pasupuleti, Mannat Singh, Manohar Paluri, Marcin Kardas, Mathew Oldham, Mathieu Rita, Maya Pavlova, Melanie Kambadur, Mike Lewis, Min Si, Mitesh Kumar Singh, Mona Hassan, Naman Goyal, Narjes Torabi, Nikolay Bashlykov, Nikolay Bogoychev, Niladri Chatterji, Olivier Duchenne, Onur Celebi, Patrick Alrassy, Pengchuan Zhang, Pengwei Li, Petar Vasic, Peter Weng, Prajjwal Bhargava, Pratik Dubal, Praveen Krishnan, Punit Singh Koura, Puxin Xu, Qing He, Qingxiao Dong, Ragavan Srinivasan, Raj Ganapathy, Ramon Calderer, Ricardo Silveira Cabral, Robert Stojnic, Roberta Raileanu, Rohit Girdhar, Rohit Patel, Roman Sauvestre, Ronnie Polidoro, Roshan Sumbaly, Ross Taylor, Ruan Silva, Rui Hou, Rui Wang, Saghar Hosseini, Sahana Chennabasappa, Sanjay Singh, Sean Bell, Seohyun Sonia Kim, Sergey Edunov, Shaoliang Nie, Sharan Narang, Sharath Rapparthi, Sheng Shen, Shengye Wan, Shruti Bhosale, Shun Zhang, Simon Vandenhende, Soumya Batra, Spencer Whitman, Sten Sootla, Stephane Collot, Suchin Gururangan, Sydney Borodinsky, Tamar Herman, Tara Fowler, Tarek Sheasha, Thomas Georgiou, Thomas

Scialom, Tobias Speckbacher, Todor Mihaylov, Tong Xiao, Ujjwal Karn, Vedanuj Goswami, Vibhor Gupta, Vignesh Ramanathan, Viktor Kerkez, Vincent Gouget, Virginie Do, Vish Vogeti, Vladan Petrovic, Weiwei Chu, Wenhan Xiong, Wenyin Fu, Whitney Meers, Xavier Martinet, Xiaodong Wang, Xiaoqing Ellen Tan, Xinfeng Xie, Xuchao Jia, Xuewei Wang, Yaelle Goldschlag, Yashesh Gaur, Yasmine Babaei, Yi Wen, Yiwen Song, Yuchen Zhang, Yue Li, Yuning Mao, Zacharie DelPierre Coudert, Zheng Yan, Zhengxing Chen, Zoe Papanikos, Aaditya Singh, Aaron Grattafiori, Abha Jain, Adam Kelsey, Adam Shajnfeld, Adithya Gangidi, Adolfo Victoria, Ahuva Goldstand, Ajay Menon, Ajay Sharma, Alex Boesenberg, Alex Vaughan, Alexei Baevski, Allie Feinstein, Amanda Kallet, Amit Sangani, Anam Yunus, Andrei Lupu, Andres Alvarado, Andrew Caples, Andrew Gu, Andrew Ho, Andrew Poulton, Andrew Ryan, Ankit Ramchandani, Annie Franco, Aparajita Saraf, Arkabandhu Chowdhury, Ashley Gabriel, Ashwin Bharambe, Assaf Eisenman, Azadeh Yazdan, Beau James, Ben Maurer, Benjamin Leonhardi, Bernie Huang, Beth Loyd, Beto De Paola, Bhargavi Paranjape, Bing Liu, Bo Wu, Boyu Ni, Braden Hancock, Bram Wasti, Brandon Spence, Brani Stojkovic, Brian Gamido, Britt Montalvo, Carl Parker, Carly Burton, Catalina Mejia, Changhan Wang, Changkyu Kim, Chao Zhou, Chester Hu, Ching-Hsiang Chu, Chris Cai, Chris Tindal, Christoph Feichtenhofer, Damon Civin, Dana Beaty, Daniel Kreymer, Daniel Li, Danny Wyatt, David Adkins, David Xu, Davide Testuggine, Delia David, Devi Parikh, Diana Liskovich, Didem Foss, Dingkang Wang, Duc Le, Dustin Holland, Edward Dowling, Eissa Jamil, Elaine Montgomery, Eleonora Presani, Emily Hahn, Emily Wood, Erik Brinkman, Esteban Arcaute, Evan Dunbar, Evan Smothers, Fei Sun, Felix Kreuk, Feng Tian, Firat Ozgenel, Francesco Caggioni, Francisco Guzmán, Frank Kanayet, Frank Seide, Gabriela Medina Florez, Gabriella Schwarz, Gada Badeer, Georgia Swee, Gil Halpern, Govind Thattai, Grant Herman, Grigory Sizov, Guangyi Zhang, Guna Lakshminarayanan, Hamid Shojanazeri, Han Zou, Hannah Wang, Hanwen Zha, Haroun Habeeb, Harrison Rudolph, Helen Suk, Henry Aspegren, Hunter Goldman, Ibrahim Damlaj, Igor Molybog, Igor Tufanov, Irina-Elena Veliche, Itai Gat, Jake Weissman, James Geboski, James Kohli, Japhet Asher, Jean-Baptiste Gaya, Jeff Marcus, Jeff Tang, Jennifer Chan, Jenny Zhen, Jeremy Reizenstein, Jeremy Teboul, Jessica Zhong, Jian Jin, Jingyi Yang, Joe Cummings, Jon Carvill, Jon Shepard, Jonathan McPhie, Jonathan Torres, Josh Ginsburg, Junjie Wang, Kai Wu, Kam Hou U, Karan Saxena, Karthik Prasad, Kartikay Khandelwal, Katayoun Zand, Kathy Matosich, Kaushik Veeraraghavan, Kelly Michelena, Keqian Li, Kun Huang, Kunal Chawla, Kushal Lakhota, Kyle Huang, Lailin Chen, Lakshya Garg, Lavender A, Leandro Silva, Lee Bell, Lei Zhang, Liangpeng Guo, Licheng Yu, Liron Moshkovich, Luca Wehrstedt, Madian Khabsa, Manav Avalani, Manish Bhatt, Maria Tsimpoukelli, Martynas Mankus, Matan Hasson, Matthew Lennie, Matthias Reso, Maxim Groshev, Maxim Naumov, Maya Lathi, Meghan Keneally,

- Michael L. Seltzer, Michal Valko, Michelle Restrepo, Mihir Patel, Mik Vyatskov, Mikayel Samvelyan, Mike Clark, Mike Macey, Mike Wang, Miquel Jubert Hermoso, Mo Metanat, Mohammad Rastegari, Munish Bansal, Nandhini Santhanam, Natascha Parks, Natasha White, Navyata Bawa, Nayan Singhal, Nick Egebo, Nicolas Usunier, Nikolay Pavlovich Laptev, Ning Dong, Ning Zhang, Norman Cheng, Oleg Chernoguz, Olivia Hart, Omkar Salpekar, Ozlem Kalinli, Parkin Kent, Parth Parekh, Paul Saab, Pavan Balaji, Pedro Rittner, Philip Bontrager, Pierre Roux, Piotr Dollar, Polina Zvyagina, Prashant Ratan-chandani, Pritish Yuvraj, Qian Liang, Rachad Alao, Rachel Rodriguez, Rafi Ayub, Raghotham Murthy, Raghu Nayani, Rahul Mitra, Raymond Li, Rebekkah Hogan, Robin Battey, Rocky Wang, Rohan Maheswari, Russ Howes, Ruty Rinott, Sai Jayesh Bondu, Samyak Datta, Sara Chugh, Sara Hunt, Sargun Dhillon, Sasha Sidorov, Satadru Pan, Saurabh Verma, Seiji Yamamoto, Sharadh Ramaswamy, Shaun Lindsay, Shaun Lindsay, Sheng Feng, Shenghao Lin, Shengxin Cindy Zha, Shiva Shankar, Shuqiang Zhang, Shuqiang Zhang, Sinong Wang, Sneha Agarwal, Soji Sajuyigbe, Soumith Chintala, Stephanie Max, Stephen Chen, Steve Kehoe, Steve Satterfield, Sudarshan Govindaprasad, Sumit Gupta, Sungmin Cho, Sunny Virk, Suraj Subramanian, Sy Choudhury, Sydney Goldman, Tal Remez, Tamar Glaser, Tamara Best, Thilo Kohler, Thomas Robinson, Tianhe Li, Tianjun Zhang, Tim Matthews, Timothy Chou, Tzook Shaked, Varun Vontimitta, Victoria Ajayi, Victoria Montanez, Vijai Mohan, Vinay Satish Kumar, Vishal Mangla, Vitor Albiero, Vlad Ionescu, Vlad Poenaru, Vlad Tiberiu Mihalescu, Vladimir Ivanov, Wei Li, Wenchen Wang, Wenwen Jiang, Wes Bouaziz, Will Constable, Xiaocheng Tang, Xiaofang Wang, Xiaojian Wu, Xiaolan Wang, Xide Xia, Xilun Wu, Xinbo Gao, Yanjun Chen, Ye Hu, Ye Jia, Ye Qi, Yenda Li, Yilin Zhang, Ying Zhang, Yossi Adi, Youngjin Nam, Yu, Wang, Yuchen Hao, Yundi Qian, Yuzi He, Zach Rait, Zachary DeVito, Zef Rosnbrick, Zhaoduo Wen, Zhenyu Yang, and Zhiwei Zhao. 2024. *The llama 3 herd of models*. *Preprint*, arXiv:2407.21783.
- Dirk Groeneveld, Iz Beltagy, Evan Pete Walsh, Akshita Bhagia, Rodney Kinney, Oyvind Tafjord, Ananya Harsh Jha, Hamish Ivison, Ian Magnusson, Yizhong Wang, Shane Arora, David Atkinson, Russell Authur, Khyathi Raghavi Chandu, Arman Cohan, Jennifer Dumas, Yanai Elazar, Yuling Gu, Jack Hessel, Tushar Khot, William Merrill, Jacob Morrison, Niklas Muennighoff, Aakanksha Naik, Crystal Nam, Matthew E. Peters, Valentina Pyatkin, Abhilasha Ravichander, Dustin Schwenk, Saurabh Shah, Will Smith, Emma Strubell, Nishant Subramani, Mitchell Wortsman, Pradeep Dasigi, Nathan Lambert, Kyle Richardson, Luke Zettlemoyer, Jesse Dodge, Kyle Lo, Luca Soldaini, Noah A. Smith, and Hannaneh Hajishirzi. 2024. Olmo: Accelerating the science of language models. In *ACL (1)*, pages 15789–15809. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Dan Hendrycks, Collin Burns, Steven Basart, Andy Zou, Mantas Mazeika, Dawn Song, and Jacob Steinhardt. 2021. Measuring massive multitask language understanding. In *ICLR*. OpenReview.net.
- Albert Q. Jiang, Alexandre Sablayrolles, Arthur Mensch, Chris Bamford, Devendra Singh Chaplot, Diego de Las Casas, Florian Bressand, Gianna Lengyel, Guillaume Lample, Lucile Saulnier, Léo Renard Lavaud, Marie-Anne Lachaux, Pierre Stock, Teven Le Scao, Thibaut Lavril, Thomas Wang, Timothée Lacroix, and William El Sayed. 2023. Mistral 7b. *CoRR*, abs/2310.06825.
- Vijay Anand Korthikanti, Jared Casper, Sangkug Lym, Lawrence McAfee, Michael Andersch, Mohammad Shoeybi, and Bryan Catanzaro. 2023. Reducing activation recomputation in large transformer models. *Proceedings of Machine Learning and Systems*, 5:341–353.
- Guillaume Lample and Alexis Conneau. 2019. *Cross-lingual language model pretraining*. *Preprint*, arXiv:1901.07291.
- Stephanie Lin, Jacob Hilton, and Owain Evans. 2022. Truthfulqa: Measuring how models mimic human falsehoods. In *ACL (1)*, pages 3214–3252. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Pedro Henrique Martins, Patrick Fernandes, João Alves, Nuno M Guerreiro, Ricardo Rei, Duarte M Alves, José Pombal, Amin Farajian, Manuel Faysse, Mateusz Klimaszewski, et al. 2024. Eurollm: Multilingual language models for europe. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.16235*.
- Aleksandar Petrov, Emanuele La Malfa, Philip H. S. Torr, and Adel Bibi. 2023. Language model tokenizers introduce unfairness between languages. In *NeurIPS*.
- Teven Le Scao, Angela Fan, Christopher Akiki, Ellie Pavlick, Suzana Ilic, Daniel Hesslow, Roman Castagné, Alexandra Sasha Luccioni, François Yvon, Matthias Gallé, Jonathan Tow, Alexander M. Rush, Stella Biderman, Albert Webson, Pawan Sasanka Ammanamanchi, Thomas Wang, Benoît Sagot, Niklas Muennighoff, Albert Villanova del Moral, Olatunji Ruwase, Rachel Bawden, Stas Bekman, Angelina McMillan-Major, Iz Beltagy, Huu Nguyen, Lucile Saulnier, Samson Tan, Pedro Ortiz Suarez, Victor Sanh, Hugo Laurençon, Yacine Jernite, Julien Launay, Margaret Mitchell, Colin Raffel, Aaron Gokaslan, Adi Simhi, Aitor Soroa, Alham Fikri Aji, Amit Alfassy, Anna Rogers, Ariel Kreisberg Nitzav, Canwen Xu, Chenghao Mou, Chris Emezue, Christopher Klamm, Colin Leong, Daniel van Strien, David Ifeoluwa Adelani, and et al. 2022. BLOOM: A 176b-parameter open-access multilingual language model. *CoRR*, abs/2211.05100.
- Jianlin Su, Murtadha H. M. Ahmed, Yu Lu, Shengfeng Pan, Wen Bo, and Yunfeng Liu. 2024. Roformer: Enhanced transformer with rotary position embedding. *Neurocomputing*, 568:127063.

- Hugo Touvron, Thibaut Lavril, Gautier Izacard, Xavier Martinet, Marie-Anne Lachaux, Timothée Lacroix, Baptiste Rozière, Naman Goyal, Eric Hambro, Faisal Azhar, Aurélien Rodriguez, Armand Joulin, Edouard Grave, and Guillaume Lample. 2023a. Llama: Open and efficient foundation language models. *CoRR*, abs/2302.13971.
- Hugo Touvron, Louis Martin, Kevin Stone, Peter Albert, Amjad Almahairi, Yasmine Babaei, Nikolay Bashlykov, Soumya Batra, Prajjwal Bhargava, Shruti Bhosale, Dan Bikel, Lukas Blecher, Cristian Canton-Ferrer, Moya Chen, Guillem Cucurull, David Esioibu, Jude Fernandes, Jeremy Fu, Wenyin Fu, Brian Fuller, Cynthia Gao, Vedanuj Goswami, Naman Goyal, Anthony Hartshorn, Saghar Hosseini, Rui Hou, Hakan Inan, Marcin Kardas, Viktor Kerkez, Madian Khabsa, Isabel Kloumann, Artem Korenev, Punit Singh Koura, Marie-Anne Lachaux, Thibaut Lavril, Jenya Lee, Diana Liskovich, Yinghai Lu, Yunying Mao, Xavier Martinet, Todor Mihaylov, Pushkar Mishra, Igor Molybog, Yixin Nie, Andrew Poulton, Jeremy Reizenstein, Rashi Rungta, Kalyan Saladi, Alan Schelten, Ruan Silva, Eric Michael Smith, Ranjan Subramanian, Xiaoqing Ellen Tan, Binh Tang, Ross Taylor, Adina Williams, Jian Xiang Kuan, Puxin Xu, Zheng Yan, Iliyan Zarov, Yuchen Zhang, Angela Fan, Melanie Kambadur, Sharan Narang, Aurélien Rodriguez, Robert Stojnic, Sergey Edunov, and Thomas Scialom. 2023b. Llama 2: Open foundation and fine-tuned chat models. *CoRR*, abs/2307.09288.
- Ahmet Üstün, Viraat Aryabumi, Zheng Xin Yong, Wei-Yin Ko, Daniel D'souza, Gbemileke Onilude, Neel Bhandari, Shivalika Singh, Hui-Lee Ooi, Amr Kayid, Freddie Vargus, Phil Blunsom, Shayne Longpre, Niklas Muennighoff, Marzieh Fadaee, Julia Kreutzer, and Sara Hooker. 2024. Aya model: An instruction finetuned open-access multilingual language model. In *ACL (1)*, pages 15894–15939. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Ashish Vaswani, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N. Gomez, Lukasz Kaiser, and Illia Polosukhin. 2017. Attention is all you need. In *NIPS*, pages 5998–6008.
- Alexander Arno Weber, Klaudia Thellmann, Jan Ebert, Nicolas Flores-Herr, Jens Lehmann, Michael Fromm, and Mehdi Ali. 2024. [Investigating multilingual instruction-tuning: Do polyglot models demand for multilingual instructions?](#) *CoRR*, abs/2402.13703.
- Haoran Xu, Young Jin Kim, Amr Sharaf, and Hany Hassan Awadalla. 2024. [A paradigm shift in machine translation: Boosting translation performance of large language models.](#) In *The Twelfth International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2024, Vienna, Austria, May 7-11, 2024*. OpenReview.net.
- Linting Xue, Noah Constant, Adam Roberts, Mihir Kale, Rami Al-Rfou, Aditya Siddhant, Aditya Barua, and Colin Raffel. 2021. mt5: A massively multilingual pre-trained text-to-text transformer. In *NAACL-HLT*, pages 483–498. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Rowan Zellers, Ari Holtzman, Yonatan Bisk, Ali Farhadi, and Yejin Choi. 2019. Hellaswag: Can a machine really finish your sentence? In *ACL (1)*, pages 4791–4800. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Susan Zhang, Stephen Roller, Naman Goyal, Mikel Artetxe, Moya Chen, Shuohui Chen, Christopher Dewan, Mona T. Diab, Xian Li, Xi Victoria Lin, Todor Mihaylov, Myle Ott, Sam Shleifer, Kurt Shuster, Daniel Simig, Punit Singh Koura, Anjali Sridhar, Tianlu Wang, and Luke Zettlemoyer. 2022. OPT: open pre-trained transformer language models. *CoRR*, abs/2205.01068.

A Appendix

A.1 Data

A.1.1 Dumps

In this section, we outline the Common Crawl data utilized in our LLM training, detailing the cutoff dates and the data collection period. The dumps span multiple years, with varying distributions of weeks per year (cf. Table 7), which is critical for understanding the temporal coverage of the training data.

Year	Week
2014	42
2015	14, 48
2016	22, 44
2017	13, 47, 51
2018	5, 9, 13, 17, 22, 26, 30, 34, 39, 43, 47, 51
2019	4, 9, 13, 18, 22, 26, 30, 35, 39, 47, 51
2020	5, 10, 16, 24, 29, 34, 40, 45, 50
2021	4, 10, 17, 21, 25, 31, 39, 43, 49
2022	5, 21, 27, 33, 40, 49
2023	6, 14, 23, 40, 50

Table 7: List of dumps by year and week.

The data spans from 2014 to 2023, with earlier years (2014-2016) containing fewer dumps but often representing a larger dataset per dump. The latest available data cutoff is from 2023 (week 50), giving the model a comprehensive span of nearly a decade of web data.

This periodization ensures that the model has exposure to a wide temporal range of web content, with a balanced emphasis on both earlier, higher-density dumps and more recent, frequent dumps, providing a robust training corpus.

A.2 Instruction-tuning Evaluation Results

In ?? we present the evaluation results of MT-Bench-X (Weber et al., 2024). For the discussion of the results, we refer to Section 6.3.

LAN	Curated (M)	Web (M)	Curated in %	Total (M)	%
bg	21 233	23 810	47.14	45 042	1.13
cs	6 229	46 919	11.72	53 148	1.33
da	6 220	18 257	25.41	24 477	0.61
de	36 850	312 006	10.56	348 856	8.72
el	21 078	40 494	34.23	61 572	1.54
en	215 204	1 452 819	12.90	1 668 024	41.70
es	23 788	295 850	7.44	319 638	7.99
et	8 785	6 253	58.42	15 038	0.38
fi	3 234	35 996	8.24	39 231	0.98
fr	30 606	333 399	8.41	364 005	9.10
ga	474	75	86.26	549	0.01
hr	15 296	1	99.99	15 298	0.38
hu	3 376	37 551	8.25	40 927	1.02
it	19 834	169 069	10.50	188 903	4.72
lt	1 990	9 141	17.88	11 131	0.28
lv	1 980	5 683	25.84	7 663	0.19
mt	3 515	0.5	99.99	3 516	0.09
nl	6 788	125 106	5.15	131 893	3.30
pl	9 397	67 361	12.24	76 758	1.92
pt	6 670	136 284	4.67	142 954	3.57
ro	4 524	25 988	14.83	30 512	0.76
sk	40 114	11 162	78.23	51 276	1.28
sl	12 599	1 228	91.12	13 827	0.35
sv	4 079	40 070	9.24	44 148	1.10
code	301 612	-	100.00	301 612	7.54
Total	805 477	3 194 523	51.57	4 000 000	100.00

Table 8: Comparison of token counts (in millions) between curated and web data across different languages. The total word count reflects the sum of both curated and web-sourced data after deduplication and filtering. Source code is treated separately from natural language data.

Table 9: Overview of large-scale multilingual and domain-specific datasets, including their respective word counts and usage percentages across various sectors such as source code, academia, law, medicine, and open knowledge bases. Each dataset's URL provides access to further information.

Name	Language/s	Domain	# Words	Percentage
StarCoder data	CODE	Source Code	73.064.206.834	25,35%
peS2o	EN	Academic	42.172.944.553	14,63%
MaCoCu	EU24	Web	27.930.391.197	9,69%
Legal MC4	EU24	Law and Admin.	13.892.450.758	4,82%
European Union Law: EurLex	EU24	Law and Admin.	13.235.730.604	4,59%
Pile: PMC extracts	EN	Medical	12.113.007.827	4,20%
Wikimedia: Wikipedia	EU24	Knowledge Base	11.382.015.197	3,95%
Pile: Openwebtext2	EN	Books	10.633.550.340	3,69%
Pile: Free law opinions V2	EN	Law and Admin.	10.408.105.722	3,61%
RedPajama: arXiv	EN	Academic	10.202.502.052	3,54%
OpenWebMath	EN	Math	7.378.503.091	2,56%
StackExchange	EN	Forum	7.311.540.145	2,54%
Wacky (ukWaC, deWaC, itWaC, frWaC)	EN,DE,IT	Web	6.440.088.223	2,23%
Kleine (und große) Anfragen	DE	Law and Admin.	6.151.085.999	2,13%
Proof pile	EN	Math	4.495.525.078	1,56%
Projekt Gutenberg	EU24	Books	3.374.582.910	1,17%
Pile: PMC abstracts	EN	Medical	3.173.320.716	1,10%
Norwegian Colossal Corpus (NCC)	NO	Knowledge Base	2.920.299.614	1,01%
SK court decisions	SVK	Law and Admin.	2.174.828.161	0,75%
Opensubtitles 2018	EU24	Culture	1.398.063.978	0,49%
Spanish legal corpra	ES	Law and Admin.	1.383.749.504	0,48%
Multilingual European Union Law: MultiEurLex	EU24	Law and Admin.	1.184.706.666	0,41%
Digital Corpus of the European Parliament: DCEP	EU24	Law and Admin.	1.117.868.910	0,39%
Multi UN corpus: MultiUN	EU24	Law and Admin.	1.096.690.756	0,38%
ParlaMint corpus of parliamentary debates	EU24	Law and Admin.	1.095.629.337	0,38%
Admin EUR corpus of EU legislation	EU24	Law and Admin.	1.079.748.261	0,37%
Estonian National Corpus 2021: ENC 2021	EU24	Web	1.004.815.512	0,35%
slWaC	SL	Web	953.803.486	0,33%
Danish Gigaword: DaGW	DA	Web	922.700.245	0,32%
Wikimedia: WikiSource	EU24	Books	798.322.622	0,28%

German Court Decision Dataset	DE	Law and Admin.	749.060.810	0,26%
European Parliament: EuroParl	EU24	Law and Admin.	660.716.717	0,23%
Swiss policy documents	DE,FR,IT	Law and Admin.	561.574.452	0,19%
Corpus der Drucksachen des Deutschen Bundestages	DE	Law and Admin.	515.053.512	0,18%
Pile: Philarchive V2	EN	Academic	487.032.008	0,17%
Polish Parliamentary Corpus: PPC	PL	Law and Admin.	472.193.828	0,16%
MARCELL CEF: MARCELL	BG,HR,HU,RO,SL,SK,PL	Law and Admin.	373.283.188	0,13%
OpenLegalData	DE	Law and Admin.	363.962.090	0,13%
Pile: NIH exporter	EN	Medical	307.055.044	0,11%
Korpus Malti	MA	Web	276.204.170	0,10%
Pile: HackerNews	EN	Web	246.149.295	0,09%
Corpus der Plenarprotokolle des Deutschen Bundestages	DE	Law and Admin.	235.502.510	0,08%
AmpsMath: Mathematica	EN	Math	232.502.096	0,08%
Estonian Reference Corpus	ET	Web	227.978.247	0,08%
Paisa	IT	Web	207.382.616	0,07%
Deutsches TextArchiv: DTA	DE	Books	197.339.728	0,07%
Wikimedia: WikiBooks	EU24	Books	168.473.660	0,06%
European Medicines Agency Corpus: EMEA	EU24	Medical	152.252.365	0,05%
Wikimedia: WikiQuote	EU24	Recreation	146.497.554	0,05%
Swiss Judgment Prediction	DE,FR	Law and Admin.	144.599.546	0,05%
WikiHow	EN	Knowledge Base	109.611.227	0,04%
Corpus der Entscheidungen: Bundesgerichtshofs	DE	Law and Admin.	104.002.842	0,04%
Multilingual Medical Corpora	DE,EN,ES,FR	Medical	90.741.906	0,03%
SE times corpus	BG,BS,EL,EN,HR,MK,RO,SQ,TR	News	69.279.571	0,02%
Wikimedia: Wikivoyage	EU24	Culture	66.278.289	0,02%
Corpus der Entscheidungen: Bundespatentgerichts	DE	Law and Admin.	66.029.205	0,02%
Wikiversity	EU24	Books	65.482.211	0,02%
EventCorefBank: EC	EU24	Finance	53.894.980	0,02%
Drug Information Corpus: Medi-Notice	DE,FR,IT	Medical	52.068.268	0,02%
Corpus der Entscheidungen: Bundesverwaltungsgerichts	DE	Law and Admin.	49.664.175	0,02%
Seimas transcripts	EN,LT	Law and Admin.	47.319.919	0,02%
Wikimedia: WikiNews	EU24	News	46.936.064	0,02%
Irish legislation	GA	Law and Admin.	29.136.258	0,01%

Greek legal code	EL	Law and Admin.	28.791.315	0,01%
Corpus of Decisions: International Court of Justice	EN, FR	Law and Admin.	25.979.848	0,01%
PRINCIPLE Anonymized English-Irish DCHG	GA,EN	Law and Admin.	25.776.098	0,01%
Corpus der Entscheidungen: Bundesfinanzhofs	DE	Law and Admin.	22.635.865	0,01%
Corpus der Entscheidungen: Bundesverfassungsgerichts	DE	Law and Admin.	20.679.001	0,01%
Corpus der Entscheidungen: Bundesarbeitsgerichts	DE	Law and Admin.	18.487.621	0,01%
AmpsMath: Khan	EN	Math	12.081.447	0,00%
German Polticial Speeches Corpus	DE	Law and Admin.	11.366.979	0,00%
Swiss Legislation Corpus (SLC)	DE,FR	Law and Admin.	10.407.743	0,00%
Finnish Language Text Corpus: FI news	FI	News	3.650.602	0,00%
Corpus of Contemporary Irish: Gaois corpus	GA	Law and Admin.	2.168.867	0,00%
Corpus of Decisions: Permanent Court of International Justice	EN	Law and Admin.	2.117.333	0,00%